

ANALYSIS OF WATER CIRCULATION ON IZMIT BAY UNDER DIFFERENT METEOROLOGICAL CONDITIONS WITH MITGCM

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Abstract

We used the MITgcm model with Orlanski boundary conditions and process-oriented modeling to examine the sensitivity of the Izmit Bay water circulation to wind speed, direction, and duration. The simulations demonstrated that there is little variation in seawater temperature, salinity, or stratification under modest forcing. Depending on the direction, substantial forcing at wind speeds of 4.9 m/s, 6.7 m/s, and 10.1 m/s produces notable and sub-mesoscale processes. Easterly component winds raises subsurface waters to the surface, whereas westerly component winds causes downwelling over the eastern shore. It is found that the hydrography of the bay is open to be largely impacted by extreme wind occurrences that exceeded 4.9 m/s.

Keywords: *Air-sea interactions, Marmara Sea, Salinity, Wind, Upwelling*

In the study, we investigated the sensitivity of Izmit Bay to the wind, which is one of the most important driver of the Bay [1]. First, we classified the wind speeds using data from the weather station located on the nearest breakwater, Tuzla Breakwater. In addition, we built up a regional ocean circulation model by customizing the MITgcm based on the previous studies [2,3,4]. Since we followed the process-oriented hydrodynamic modeling [5], we omitted all forcing factors except the wind stress. The simulations were initiated with a state at rest and the forcing was gradually increased to the idealized wind speeds to avoid unwanted gravity waves. The runtime of the simulations is 11 days, the optimum runtime to balance computation cost and obtain distinctive model results. A late summer measurement was preferred for the homogeneous initial condition. The results of 48 adiabatic simulations are limited to the first 60 meters of depth due to negligible changes below 60 meters.

The simulation results indicate that the bay experiences quasi-stationary conditions or remains stagnant at weak wind speeds of 1.3 (10%), 2.1 (25%), and 3.3 (50%) m/s. The stagnancy of the bay under calm or weak wind conditions can encourage the degradation of the water quality because the bay is always under severe anthropogenic pressures. This can result in hypoxia or worse, eutrophic conditions, mucous formations and accumulations, heavy metal loads in sediment and biota, and a longer recovery period following any environmental disaster.

Fig. 1. Final profiles of salinity in the central basin after 11-day runtime with the initial conditions.

Stronger wind speeds (4.9 (75%), 6.7 (90%), and 10.1 (99%) m/s) show how the direction of the wind affects the forcing. The upper layer converges towards the east due to onshore winds, which have a west component, creating a deeper upper layer. The upper layer is transported outside the bay by winds with an east component, or offshore winds, which produce a jet that travels at around 50 cm/s. This jet breaches the permanent stratification, generates upwelling zones, and causes an overturning circulation in the bay. The greatest fluctuation in salinity and surface temperature is simulated under the NE 6.7 m/s forcing, which also produces the most remarkable upwelling event. A more salinized water mass is transformed at the top layer and accelerated westward, out of the bay, despite the forcing being adiabatic between the air and the sea. These

mixing mechanisms under heavy winds were characterized by Altioğ et al. [6] as the dominance of shear and the decrease in buoyancy frequency leading to mixing. The modeling results in our investigation are consistent with the storm-driven impacts reported before [7]. The results further show that the abrupt cooling (up to 5 °C) during strong wind events, one of which was observed by Tugrul et al. [8], is mostly caused by mechanical interactions. On February 13, 1975, the surface salinity was measured at 24 ppt. On February 24, eleven days after the scientific mission of Tugrul et al. began, the 10 m/s northeasterly wind caused an almost 5 ppt increase in the surface salinity [8].

It was discovered that the water circulation in Izmit Bay is also very sensitive to the wind's strength, direction, and duration, the bay's size and form, the vertical stratification, and the oceanographic conditions in the nearby offshore region. Severe winds are shown to have the power to control the mixing and water exchange across basins, as well as to shape the physical characteristics of strata down to a depth of sixty meters. Additionally, narrow passages prevent much water from moving between the basins, particularly because the Hersek Delta regulates both layers.

References

- 1 - Yüce, H.; Alpar, B. Subtidal Sea-Level Variations in the Sea of Marmara, Their Interactions with Neighboring Seas and Relations to Wind Forcing. *J. Coast. Res.* 1997, 1086–1092.
- 2 - Sannino, G.; Sözer, A.; Özsoy, E. A High-Resolution Modelling Study of the Turkish Straits System. *Ocean Dyn.* 2017, 67, 397–432.
- 3 - Oğuz, T.; Sur, H. I. A Numerical Modelling Study of Circulation in the Bay of Izmit: Final Report. *TÜBITAK-MRC Chem. Dep. Publ. Kocaeli Turk.* 1986, No. 187, 97.
- 4 - Ilicak, M.; Federico, I.; Barletta, I.; Mutlu, S.; Karan, H.; Ciliberti, S. A.; Clementi, E.; Coppini, G.; Pinardi, N. Modeling of the Turkish Strait System Using a High Resolution Unstructured Grid Ocean Circulation Model. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2021, 9 (7), 769.
- 5 - Kämpf, J.; Möller, L.; Baring, R.; Shute, A.; Cheesman, C. The Island Mass Effect: A Study of Wind-Driven Nutrient Upwelling around Reef Islands. *J. Oceanogr.* 2023, 79 (2), 161–174.
- 6 - Altioğ, H.; Can, L.; Mutlu, S. Daily Variations in Stratification in Izmit Bay. *Turk. J. Earth Sci.* 2020, 29 (5), 815–829.
- 7 - Chiggiato, J.; Jarosz, E.; Book, J. W.; Dykes, J.; Torrisi, L.; Poulain, P.-M.; Gerin, R.; Horstmann, J.; Besiktepe, S. Dynamics of the Circulation in the Sea of Marmara: Numerical Modeling Experiments and Observations from the Turkish Straits System Experiment. *Ocean Dyn.* 2012, 62 (1), 139–159.
- 8 - Tugrul, S.; Sunay, M.; Bastürk, Ö.; Balkas, T. I. The Izmit Bay Case Study. In *The Role of the Oceans as a Waste Disposal Option*; Kullenberg, G., Ed.; Springer Netherlands: Dordrecht, 1986; pp 243–274.